

Influence of Attitudinal Adaptability and Intrapersonal Skills on Grade 8 Students' Mathematics Performance

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Attitudinal adaptability and intrapersonal skills of students are essential in the learning process, especially in mathematics. Literature have proven that these factors are significantly associated with mathematics performance. This correlational explanatory study aimed to determine whether attitudinal adaptability and intrapersonal skills are significant predictors of mathematics performance. The respondents were 447 grade 8 students in a public school in Laguna, Philippines, in 2018-2019. The researcher selected them through multi-stage stratified sampling, and they responded to the adapted, validated, and highly reliable research instrument. The researcher used the multiple linear regression stepwise method in this study. The findings revealed that only intrapersonal skills ($B=.409$, $p<.01$) was the significant predictor of mathematics performance. Attitudinal adaptability was not a significant predictor in the model ($p>.05$). The ANOVA for regression showed that there was a linear association between intrapersonal skills and mathematics performance ($F_{(1,444)}=8.154$, $p=.004$). The R^2 of .018 signifies that intrapersonal skills explain 1.8% of the variation in respondents' mathematics performance, which is very low. The regression model of this study was *Mathematics performance* = $1.412 + (.409 \times \text{Intrapersonal Skills})$. When the students' level of intrapersonal skills increases, their mathematics performance also increases.

Keywords: *Attitudinal Adaptability, Intrapersonal Skills, Mathematics Performance*

Reference:

Munda, N. P. (2023). Influence of attitudinal adaptability and intrapersonal skills on grade 8 students' Mathematics performance. *Teachers' Guide: An International Monthly News-Magazine on Teaching & Learning*, 1(8), 15. <http://tinyurl.com/4raabdw2>